

Unsupervised Learning of Sparse Facial Movements using Convolutional Spiking Neural Networks

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Abstract— This contribution explores the use of a single task-dependant 3D convolutional spiking neural layer for recognizing subtle facial expressions. Using biologically inspired mechanisms like STDP, latency coding and task specific knowledge, we show that even with a shallow architecture, one can improve the learning of meaningful spatio-temporal features.

I. INTRODUCTION

Spiking neural networks (SNNs) are efficient alternatives to conventional networks for temporal pattern recognition. El Assal [1] applied 3D spiking convolutions to detect **broad and dense motion** in action recognition tasks. In contrast, this work focuses on **sparse and subtle** facial movements [2], using a simplified setup with a single 3D convolutional layer. Instead of depth, we emphasize targeted sampling and spatio-temporal sensitivity to adapt SNNs to fine-grained facial expression analysis.

II. METHODS

The overall architecture is presented in Figure 1. Grayscale video input is preprocessed using on-center/off-center filtering to enhance edges and contrast. Pixel intensities are then encoded into spike timings through latency coding. These spikes are processed by a single 3D spiking convolutional layer, where Integrate-and-Fire (IF) neurons accumulate input until a threshold is reached, emitting a spike and resetting. Synaptic weights are updated using STDP, while threshold adaptation stabilizes activity. Output spikes are pooled spatio-temporally, decoded and sent to a linear SVM for classification. The architecture remains shallow but captures dynamic facial features by combining biological plausibility with spatio-temporal filtering.

Fig. 1. Global view of the classification pipeline

To ensure meaningful feature learning we adapt the convolution layer to learn only from samples situated in relevant facial regions. We then push the convolution to learn filters reflecting the task at hand. Instead of random point selection

in the frame, we used elliptical masks: one covering the full face and another with multiple smaller ellipses over expressive areas like the eyes, mouth, and cheeks. Points were sampled uniformly within these ellipses to prioritize motion-rich regions.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The evaluation used 10-fold stratified cross-validation on the CK+ dataset with 9 runs using preset seeds for reproducibility. Each fold preserved balanced emotion classes, and preprocessing included facial landmark alignment to standardize expression features. This protocol enabled consistent performance comparisons across sampling strategies and hyperparameter configurations over 2970 experiments per strategy.

Fig. 2. Used Sampling Methods

Three sampling methods were tested (Figure 2): full-frame, full-face ellipse, and multi-region ellipses. The full-face ellipse gave the most stable performance with lowest variance. Focused sampling led to more distinct and diverse filter activations. Temporal pooling (best at 4), spatial pooling (set to 8), and filter depth (best at 3) were the most impactful hyperparameters. The optimal setup used $7 \times 7 \times 3$ filters, highlighting the value of the spatial and temporal context in shallow networks.

The full-face ellipse sampling achieved the best performance highlighting the importance of tailoring sampling strategies to the specific requirements of shallow networks. Qualitative analysis showed that filters learned from focused areas developed more distinct and diverse activation patterns.

REFERENCES

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